

OPTIMIZATION OF UNMANNED AIRCRAFT ASSEMBLY PROCESS WITH PRODUCT WORK BREAKDOWN STRUCTURE (PWBS) METHOD

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Abstract – The manufacture of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV) requires a process in its design which includes aircraft design (fuselage, wing, horizontal stabilizer, vertical stabilizer, aileron, elevator, and tail boom). The many components in the UAV cause the duration of its manufacture to take a long time. Therefore, a detailed division/planning of work is needed which is permanently grouped based on its characteristics and classification by taking into account the attributes of design and manufacture. This study aims to determine the optimal time and critical path of the UAV assembly process with the product work breakdown structure (PWBS) approach. The results showed that the optimal time for the UAV assembly process was 139 minutes. Finally, product-oriented division of work structure and optimization by paying attention to the assembly process contained in the critical path can shorten the duration of UAV assembly.

Keywords: UAV, product-oriented, critical path

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicle (UAV) is an unmanned aircraft that can be controlled by remote control. UAVs are widely used for civil needs, especially in the fields of business, industry and logistics. In the business industry, drones have been applied in various services such as infrastructure supervision, package delivery, forest fire fighting, exploration of mining materials, mapping of agricultural areas, and mapping of industrial areas. There are two variations of aircraft control, namely by remote control (transmitter) and aircraft that fly independently (autonomous). The design process to make a UAV which includes the design process of the aircraft model (fuselage, wing, nose, horizontal stabilizer, vertical stabilizer, aileron, elevator, and

tail boom) is very difficult to do because it requires technical analysis that is interconnected between components with one another. The number of UAV components that are designed and variations in the production process cause the long duration needed to produce a UAV. Several specific parameters of the classification system such as shape, dimensions, tolerances, materials as well as the type and complexity of the production machine operation are considered in the UAV assembly process.

The number of activities in the manufacture of UAVs causes the need for systematic planning which is determined through an effective and optimal time in the assembly process. In the following, the grouping of product-oriented assembly activities and the process of optimizing the unmanned aircraft assembly process will be presented using the Critical Path Method (CPM) approach. This method is used to determine the critical path of the assembly process so that the optimal time will be obtained in the assembly process.

II. STUDY OF LITERATURE

An information system is an organized collection of people, information technology, information resources, and all coordinated activities to achieve certain objectives in the business organization. Conceptually, an information system may or may not be computerized. Information systems analysis and design refers to the process of completing an information system development project. Information system development covers a wide range of technical areas including business process modeling, data modeling and database design, networking design, computer programming, and computer hardware and operating systems. Practically, the information systems analysis and design focus on two components: management of information systems development and business

process modeling, and touch on other technical areas very briefly when delivering the monolithic concept of information systems development.

System development life cycle (SDLC) is a conceptual model of the phases an information system goes through. The typical systems development life cycle model suggest five fundamental phases of information systems development process: planning, analysis, design, implementation, and maintenance.

The planning phase is the process of preliminary investigation to understand why a new information system should be created for the organization. The deliverable of the planning phase includes a report of the feasibility study and the workplan for the new information system development project. Once the organization decides to create a new information system, a full-scale project of information system development is then started.

The analysis phase is the first stage of the full-scale information system development project to investigate what the new information system will do. In this phase, the project team fully investigate the current information system (on the as-is system) of the organization and the specific business needs (or the system requirements) for the new information system. The new information system that meets the system requirements is called the to-be system. The deliverable of the analysis phase reports on the following major system analysis results.

The design phase determines how the to-be system will be created and how it will operate in terms of hardware, software, networking, system personnel, and operational procedures. The deliverables of the design phase are the detailed system specifications of system infrastructure, hardware, software, and networking for the implementation phase. The design phase actually provides the solution to the to-be system.

The implementation phase builds the new information system based on the system specification provided by the design phase. The methods applied to the system implementation phase vary depending on the strategies of system development. By the end of the implementation phase, the new information system replaces the old information system.

The maintenance phase improves the new information system. Because of the innovation of

information technology and significant changes of the business environment, the cost of system maintenance eventually becomes unjustified at a certain point. The next generation of information system in the organization will be inevitable. The information system development start a new cycle.

III. DISCUSSION

3.1. UAV Design Specification

UAV designed has a total weight specification is 1.75 kg with minimum flight speed 12m/s (Low Speed Stall). The plane must capable to flight in slow speed up to 12 m/s to be stable when taking photos aerial and video monitoring. The UAV that will be designed and built can seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1. UAV Design

The determination of the UAV design concept also consider the availability of UAV materials that easilyobtained and the aircraft manufacturing process is easy to do. Limited flight locations (disaster locations, rivers, beach, etc.), does not allow UAV take-off using landing gear. For this reason, the UAV is designed using the concept (hand launch), namely flight by throwing hands. The specifications are listed in Table 1. Below

Table 1. UAV Specification

Maximum Weight	1.75 kg
Wing Span	1800 mm
Aspect Ratio	8
Flight Speed	12 m/s
Take-Off	Hand Launch

3.2. Work Breakdown Structure (WBS)

WBS shows the overall project activities that are used as a reference for making a work schedule with the CPM method. WBS is used to divide the work in the project up to the activity level. The WBS system that will be applied in this study is a combination of SWBS and PWBS. The concept of Engineering, Procurement, and Construction (EPC) was adopted as one of the references in preparing the WBS. The division of the work structure of the UAV can be seen in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2. EPC concept on Work Breakdown Structure (WBS) making UAV

3.3. Product Work Breakdown Structure (PWBS)

Product Work Breakdown Structure (PWBS) can be exemplified in the Construction section. Where in the construction section, it is broken down into several main groups consisting of Airframe, Propulsion, and so on. From the main group, it will be broken down again into smaller parts according to the interim product (PWBS). The distribution scheme for the UAV system can be seen in Figure 3 below:

Figure 3. PWBS Chart on UAV Construction

3.4. Activity Identification

Figure 4. UAV Manufacturing Activity Formulation Model based on Product Work Breakdown Structure (PWBS)

This stage begins with the WBS UAV being built, followed by an interim classification of products from the main group and identifying what activities are needed. After knowing these activities, grouping the activities is carried out. The arrangement of the sequence of activities must be correct and systematic so that the project schedule can be carried out properly.

Identification of UAV manufacturing activities based on the model in Figure 4. Starting

with a breakdown of the designed UAV system. The number of activities in the manufacture of UAVs, then the grouping of direct activities is carried out, namely activities related to the process of making UAVs directly. The step of defining the activity following the flowchart can be seen in Figure 5.

Figure 6. Activity Definition Flowchart

3.5. UAV Assembly Process Optimization

In the distribution of UAV manufacturing activities, there were 85 activities. In this case, 28 assembly process activities are displayed which are divided into several locations, starting from the preparation of the wing components to the installation of the receiver.

The list of activities in Table 2 is used to form a network that is processed using the Critical Path Method (CPM). In project activities for UAV assembly, it will be known the application of the Critical Path Method (CPM) in assembling the components of the activity with the longest total amount of time and showing the fastest project completion time.

Table 2. Assembly UAV Data

Kode	Aktivitas	Predecessor	Time Duranon (mins)
0	Mulai		0
A	Persiapan Komponen Wing	-	7
B	Pemasukan Aluminium kedalam Wing	A	20
C	Pemasangan Wing	A,B	15
D	Pemasangan Rumah Wing	C	15
E	Persiapan Komponen Fuselage		5
F	Perskitan Fuselage	E	12
G	Pemasangan kedudukan Motor	F	8
H	Pemasangan Pegangan Boom	F	7
I	Pemasangan Cover Fuselage	F	10
J	Persiapan Komponen Rangka Tail		5
K	Pemasangan Rangka Tail	J	20
L	Perskitan Horizontal Stabilizer dan Vertical Stabilizer	C,K	30
M	Pemasangan Aileron	C	5
N	Pemasangan Elevator	L	5
O	Pemasangan Servo	M,N	7
P	Pemasangan Motor	G	8
Q	Pemasangan Propeler	P	1
R	Persiapan Komponen Electric		10
S	Pemasangan ESC	F,P,R	10
T	Pemasangan Battery	S	2
U	Persiapan Komponen Control		10
V	Pemasangan Kabel Servo	F,O,U	15
W	Pemasangan Aduapilot apm 2.6	T,V	25
X	Pemasangan GPS	W	15
Y	Pemasangan Telemetry	W	8
Z	Pemasangan Receiver	W	5

From the assembly data owned, there is one process with other processes that are interdependent and related. In Table 3, it is explained that levels 1-9 have a relationship with each other. Where when the assembly process is carried out, you have to wait for other processes to finish before you can proceed to the next assembly level process.

Thus, for the UAV optimization process, critical components identified during the assembly process can be considered. The faster the critical activities are carried out, the faster the UAV assembly process will be carried out.

Table 3. Assembly Level Division

Level	Kode	Aktivitas
1	A	Persiapan Komponen <i>Wing</i>
	J	Persiapan Komponen <i>Rangka</i>
	U	Persiapan Komponen <i>Control</i>
	R	Persiapan Komponen <i>Electric</i>
	E	Persiapan Komponen <i>Fuselage</i>
2	B	Pemasukan Aluminium kedalam <i>Wing</i>
	K	Pemasangan <i>Rangka Tail</i>
	F	Perakitan <i>Fuselage</i>
3	C	Pemasangan <i>Wing</i>
	G	Pemasangan Kedudukan <i>Motor</i>
	H	Pemasangan Pegangan <i>Boom</i>
	I	Pemasangan <i>Calver Fuselage</i>
4	D	Pemasangan <i>Rumah Wing</i>
	M	Pemasangan <i>Aileron</i>
	L	Perakitan <i>Horizontal Stabilizer</i> dan <i>Vertical Stabilizer</i>
	S	Pemasangan <i>ESC</i>
	P	Pemasangan <i>Motor</i>
5	N	Pemasangan <i>Elevator</i>
	T	Pemasangan <i>Battery</i>
	Q	Pemasangan <i>Propeler</i>
6	O	Pemasangan <i>Servo</i>
7	V	Pemasangan <i>Kabel Servo</i>
8	W	Pemasangan <i>Ardupilot apm 2.6</i>
9	X	Pemasangan <i>GPS</i>
	Y	Pemasangan <i>Telemetry</i>
	Z	Pemasangan <i>Receiver</i>

IV. CONCLUSION

1. Approach with Product Oriented Work Breakdown Structure (PWBS) in the manufacture of Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAV), in which the division of work activities into smaller sub-tasks becomes easier to do.
2. The fastest time required in assembling is 139 minutes consisting of a sequence of activities that follow from the critical path which has a total float value of 0.

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